

Vector-Borne Outbreaks and The Next Pandemic Threat

As the world recovers from the COVID-19 pandemic, a new and perhaps even more complex challenge is emerging: one driven by the changing dynamics of our planet itself. In July 2024, Brazilian authorities reported two deaths from Oropouche virus, marking a significant event as no fatalities from this disease had previously been documented in scientific literature (1). Although it was Brazil that registered most cases of Oropouche fever in 2024, Germany, Italy, and Spain reported multiple imported cases throughout summer 2024. Until recently, Oropouche fever was primarily transmitted through the bite of midges in the Amazon region. However, climate change, deforestation, and unplanned urbanisation have facilitated its spread to new areas and countries. The outbreaks underline the necessity for increased surveillance and characterization of the disease's evolving threat.

At the same time, the Americas are experiencing the largest dengue outbreak ever recorded. There is a substantial increase in the number of imported cases of dengue to Europe since the beginning of 2024 (2). Due to the presence of the virus transmitting vectors *Aedes albopictus* and *Aedes aegypti* and the imported cases of the diseases, there is a significant risk of transmission of dengue and chikungunya viruses in mainland Europe. *Aedes albopictus* is established in a large part of Europe, while *Aedes aegypti* has already established in some areas like Cyprus, the Black Sea, and Madeira. The risk of local transmission of chikungunya and dengue is high due to favourable conditions for vector activity and virus replication.

In addition to these outbreaks, West Nile fever continues to pose a significant public health problem globally, with its presence confirmed on all continents except Antarctica. In Europe, West Nile fever remains a concern with sporadic annual outbreaks. The virus predominantly circulates between birds and mosquitoes, particularly those of the *Culex* genus. Although human infections are incidental, recent years have seen an increase in severe cases, especially in temperate regions like Europe and North America, due to favourable conditions for mosquito vectors, like warmer temperatures and altered precipitation patterns (3). The potential for a wider spread exists, highlighting the need for robust surveillance and control measures.

Intense rainfall and flooding facilitated recent outbreaks of Rift Valley Fever in Kenya, Mayotte, Sudan, Mauritania, and Uganda. Rift Valley Fever is a deadly viral disease in domestic animals, transmitted to humans by infected mosquitoes or blood-feeding flies. These outbreaks not only affect human health but also cause significant economic damage due to livestock loss. Studies show that viral transmission is increasing in range and frequency, and climate change is likely to exacerbate the spread of Rift Valley Fever (4).

Over half of known human pathogens are expected to be aggravated by rising temperatures and extreme weather events (5). This change expands disease vector habitats and alters animal migration patterns, while global mobility and poverty facilitate disease transmission and increase human movement. The next pandemic is projected to be zoonotic, with many vector-borne diseases having zoonotic origins. This zoonotic nature complicates the control and prevention of these diseases, as it requires managing both human and animal health.

The systemic crisis and the Covid-19 pandemic revealed the vulnerability of society and health systems worldwide in the face of epidemics and pandemics. The lack of effective international

collaboration raises concerns about the viability of global health mechanisms, especially in a polarised world. Despite two years of negotiations, countries failed to agree on the text of the pandemic accord by the May 2024 deadline, with hopes now set on reaching an agreement in 2025. Progress has been made with a package of amendments to the International Health Regulations agreed by the WHO Member States in June 2024 (6).

To effectively combat future pandemics and vector-borne outbreaks, substantial investment in health systems to strengthen their resilience is crucial. Establishing contingency funds can provide the necessary financial support during crises. The breakthroughs in vaccine development driven by the Covid-19 pandemic and the introduction of the malaria vaccine highlight the critical role of preventive care and the necessity of ensuring access to vaccines and developing local production. It is essential to focus on One Health approach, supporting agriculture to ensure food security and reduce the spread of zoonotic diseases. Implementing climate adaptation measures is essential to strengthen community resilience. Public health efforts should prioritize population awareness campaigns and robust vector control measures. Strengthening collaboration between veterinarians, entomologists, public health experts, and climate scientists is crucial. Every outbreak, from Brazil to Europe, is a stark reminder that the health of humans, animals, and our environment is inextricably linked—neglecting one risks them all.

References

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